

CATEGORIES FOR CLASSIFICATION OF AIRCRAFT FLIGHT MODEL VALIDATION

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Abstract

One version of a stochastic computer simulation of airspace includes the implementation of complex, high-fidelity models of aircraft. Since the models are pre-existing, third-party developed products, these aircraft models require validation prior to implementation. Several methodologies are available to demonstrate the accuracy of these models and a variety of testers potentially involved, so a notation is proposed to describe the level of testing performed in the validation of a given model using seven fields, each making use of succinct notation. Rather than limiting those qualified to do this type of work or restrict the aircraft models available for use, this classification is proposed in order to allow for anyone to complete validation tasks and to allow for a wide variety of tasks during the course of validation, while keeping the ultimate user of the model easily and fully informed as to the level of testing done and the experience and qualifications of the tester.

Background

As part of the development of a Monte Carlo-based computer simulation capability to enable rigorous analysis of procedures, equipment, and airspace, a variety of models is required. Specifically, the simulation needs to stochastically model many components of the National Airspace System (NAS) – mechanical, electronic, and human – including navigation aids, surveillance systems (such as radar), pilots, aircraft, air traffic controllers, and weather; along with known, discrete models such as runway size and configuration, and obstacles [1]. Due to the complexity, size, schedule, and aviation safety-critical nature of the simulation development effort, a two-phased approach was proposed. Part of the second phase includes the implementation of complex, high-fidelity models of aircraft in the NAS. Developed externally and integrated, these aircraft models require validation prior to use in the simulation. With several methodologies available

to demonstrate the accuracy of these models [2] – from actually flying the computer model to collect data similarly to experimental flight testing or FAA Level D certification, to a basic observation of aircraft actions in response to varying parameters – and a variety of testers potentially involved – from test pilot school graduates and degreed, experienced professional engineers to those with potentially significantly less formal training, qualifications, or experience, a notation is proposed to describe the level of testing performed in the validation of a given model. Rather than limiting those qualified to do this type of work or restrict the aircraft models available for use only to those undergoing the highest levels of scrutiny, this methodology is proposed to (at the discretion of a given project's management) allow for anyone to complete validation tasks and allow for a wide variety of tasks undertaken in the course of validation, while keeping the ultimate user of the model fully informed (via the concise notation format) as to the level of testing done and the experience and qualifications of the tester (or test team leader in the case of larger groups).

Types of Aircraft Simulation Models

There are generally considered to be four ways to mathematically model aircraft in flight [3]. Models include the use of basic kinematics, the small perturbation theory model, the total forces and moments method, and blade element theory. Each of these methods has its own advantages and disadvantages which impact ease of implementation as well as fidelity in various flight regimes. By choosing a suitable mathematical flight model, as well as appropriate coordinate systems and other assumptions, any modern computer system is typically able to easily solve these aircraft equations of motion with the respective accuracy. While a completely accurate computation that includes all possible flight is impractical due to the formidable problem of solving the complete Navier-Stokes equations, the difference in accuracy between this exact solution and the center of mass flight path for

an aircraft using one of the four listed solution methods is generally small under the conditions of interest (i.e., laminar flow).

For the simplest simulator, a kinematic model consisting of only kinematic relations can be used [4]. Kinematics describes an object's motion using non-dynamical equations that involve only positions, velocities, and accelerations. This method does not use advanced mathematics and therefore does not load the computer process very much; unfortunately, this usually results in lower-fidelity results for some flight conditions. Based purely in physics and devoid of any type of aerodynamic or stability components, the kinematic flight simulator relies, with few exceptions, purely on the kinematic motion of the aircraft. Forces are generally not included nor are they necessary to calculate the aircraft's state. Benefits include simplified calculations enabling quicker design and software coding as well as faster calculations, no requirement for aircraft type-specific – and typically proprietary – data (e.g., lift and drag coefficients), and reduced computational workload.

Taking aircraft properties into account, the small perturbation method provides an incremental step in performance. Simplifying the nonlinear aircraft equations of motion results in the formation of the aircraft stability derivatives; these derivatives are an intuitive way of describing aircraft motion around a certain equilibrium point. However, this method is limited by this; as its name implies, the model provides a description of motion, but only around an equilibrium point. For an aircraft in a steep dive or a wide speed range this method is unable to produce accurate results; however, this model is commonly used in aircraft development and test when limited aircraft data is available.

Using the total forces and moments method, the complete nonlinear aircraft equations of motion are solved. As with all of these models, the aircraft is assumed to be a rigid body; however, the aircraft now has six degrees-of-freedom for application of all forces (i.e., linear) and moments (i.e., rotational). The forces and moments are found for an entire aircraft using various methods, including table-lookup and polynomial representation. Using various common integration algorithms, the aircraft's position is calculated as a result of these forces and moments every time step. Although

these formulations are quite detailed, there are still errors that arise from their use. If tabular data is used, it will not be smooth, but piecewise linear; this can prove to be an inadequate representation of smooth real-world data. A table also has a beginning and an end, past which there is no aircraft data. Some simulators hold the first and last values constant beyond these limits, while others extrapolate the data; either way this is not necessarily a precise representation of the actual aircraft. This method, however, is the most widely used in the simulation industry.

A final, lesser-used method employs the blade element theory, first derived for use with the analysis of helicopter rotors. In this method, the wing is split up into thin strips that are essentially two-dimensional, infinite-span airfoils. Since the aerodynamic properties of two-dimensional airfoils are readily calculated, the sum of these over the entire wing will produce the net forces on the wing and subsequently on the entire aircraft body. All of the force and moment calculations are based on the physical model described to the simulator; this is completely different than the other methods.

Whichever of these models are implemented, some level of validation them must be performed to determine the model's limitations and the accuracy with which it mimics the actual aircraft.

Simulation Model Validation

Many types of tests exist for performing simulator validation metrics; some evaluate the software code itself, while others evaluate the airframe or the pilot. These include: generalized software verification and validation/quality assurance, observation/inspection of aircraft model actions and performance, regulatory agency simulation qualification, experimental flight testing, maintenance flight testing, pilot annual standardization evaluations/instrument check rides and pilot's operating handbook (POH) comparisons.

Other tests and test formats not discussed here include: Developmental Test and Evaluation (DT&E), Operational Test and Evaluation (OT&E), and Research, Development, Test and Evaluation (RDT&E) structures.

General Software Verification and Validation

Traditional software testing includes: technical reviews (e.g., inspections, audits, group meetings, etc.), software testing (i.e., exercising a product to verify its results), and requirements verification (i.e., ensuring that a product and its testing addresses all requirements). A component of these is quality assurance (QA) testing. Tests used in software QA may include the techniques of observation (a non-functional test incorporating observation of a behavior to confirm the existence or function of a requirement) and exercise (executing the software in a manner consistent with its intended use to confirm the existence or function of a requirement).

Model Observation and Inspection

Specific uses of the two elements of QA testing include the techniques of observation and exercise. Depending on the type of model used, the only way it may be feasible to test the model due to its design (e.g., a kinematics-based model with no ability for control and test by an actual pilot manipulating flight controls – as may be the case with a model used for safety simulations, airspace/airport capacity simulations, and efficiency/queuing studies) may be through a non-functional test. In this case, the model may or may not be exercised through the use of pre-determined instructions, and then the aircraft model's actions are observed to ensure normal flight characteristics and performance.

U.S. Military Simulation Fidelity Testing

The military services have their own criteria for validating their various simulation devices. These requirements are often determined by contractual agreements between the service and the vendor; however, these agreements often default to the FAA norms. It should be noted that major differences exist between simulator specifications that cite, for example, FAA civilian transport simulator criteria as the basis for satisfactory flight characteristics, rather than requirements tailored to military pilot training as advocated by government technical personnel [5]. These differences include the methods for validating the simulator flight characteristics and in the approach to test and evaluation of the devices.

Regulatory Agency Simulation System Qualification

Various regulatory agencies are involved in determination of simulation qualification standards [6]. These agencies have well-established standards for certifying various types of flight simulation devices. Some of these agencies include the FAA in the U.S., the European Joint Airworthiness Authority (JAA) in the European Union (EU), the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) in the UK, the CAA in Australia, Transport Canada in Canada, ICAO, and the Royal Aeronautical Society (RAeS). (This section will primarily focus on the standards set forth by the FAA.)

Validation flight test data (performance, stability and control, and other necessary test parameters that are electrically or electronically recorded in an airplane using a calibrated data acquisition system of sufficient resolution and verified as accurate by the company performing the test) establish a reference set of relevant parameters to which like simulator parameters can be compared. This data is used by the FAA in the course of the qualification. The data is provided by the simulator manufacturer to the FAA in a time-history format (a presentation of the change of a variable with respect to time; it is usually in the form of a continuous data plot over the time period of interest or a printout of test parameter values recorded at multiple constant time intervals over the time period of interest). This allows for the FAA Simulator Evaluation Specialist (an FAA technical specialist trained to evaluate simulators) to fly the profiles described in AC 120-40B [7], record the desired data, plot the data versus time on the manufacturer-provided time history of the actual aircraft performing the same flight profile, and then allows for analysis with respect to the AC 120-40B-specified tolerances.

Experimental Flight Test and Aircraft Certification

Experimental Test Flights (also known as engineering, developmental, or certification flight tests) are defined as flights that are conducted to determine or demonstrate critical operating characteristics of an aircraft.

Experimental Flight Testing is used for the determination of an aircraft's flight envelope. Although simulator validation confirms rather than determines a flight envelope, there are several experimental flight tests that are appropriate to the validation task. Flight test conduct delves into aircraft performance and handling qualities (stability and control) on aircraft that have been instrumented to serve as in-flight laboratories. Military experimental test pilots (XPs; referred to as Flight Test Pilots (FTP) by the FAA and as Engineering Test Pilots by NASA) are first required to complete a year-long curriculum of considerable engineering depth and project variety.

A typical flight test program would consist of the following: high-speed taxi tests, first flight, envelope expansion (V-N diagram, maneuver limitations), flight at high angles of attack – stall, flight at high angles of attack – turning flight, airplane performance – maximum rate of climb (maximum excess power), airplane performance – maximum glide endurance (thrust required curve), handling qualities – static stability (longitudinal static stability without trim, longitudinal static stability with trim), handling qualities – dynamic stability (longitudinal dynamic stability for phugoid – long period, low frequency oscillations occurring over several seconds or even minutes, and for short-period response – short period, high frequency oscillations of less than two seconds each), lateral and directional dynamic stability cross coupling (gives rise to three possible dynamic effects: directional divergence, spiral divergence, and Dutch roll), handling qualities – control (longitudinal control, lateral control, and directional control), and engine-out performance and qualities – asymmetric.

Maintenance Test Flight Procedures

Maintenance Flight Testing (also known as production, acceptance, or functional checks) is

performed for new aircraft acceptance, post-maintenance performance confirmation, or for in-flight malfunction diagnosis. Maintenance test flights are designed to determine whether the airframe, power plant, accessories, and other items of equipment are functioning in accordance with predetermined standards while subjected to the intended operating environment. For simulator evaluation, this may be the most valuable type of testing since validation is performed to confirm that the simulator accurately mimics the actual aircraft. Maintenance test pilots are tasked with confirming that previously accepted flying qualities exist and are within acceptable limits. Military maintenance test flights are performed after all 100-hour inspections and after replacement or removal and reinstallation of any flight controls or surfaces, engines, engine controls, or gearboxes [8]. They may also be performed in some form to diagnose a performance discrepancy noted by an operational pilot or for data collection purposes. Designated maintenance pilots complete a formal course of instruction and a prescribed hands-on training syllabus.

Operational Flight Procedures

Operational flight maneuvers can be used for evaluation of a simulator in use for its intended purpose (e.g., flying instrument approaches, shipboard interface, etc.). As such, the types of evaluations performed on pilots can be used in providing a test sequence and format. Examples of typical pilot evaluations (also known as “check rides”) include training syllabus flights and annual pilot flight evaluations (consisting of normal procedures and emergency training), tactical check rides (consisting of tactical or special procedures), and instrument checks (consisting of instrument flight rules). Operational flight procedures can be used with the Cooper-Harper handling qualities scale (Figure 1) to rapidly assess the flight model.

HANDLING QUALITIES RATING SCALE

Figure 1. The Cooper-Harper Handling Qualities Scale

Pilot's Operating Handbook

The POH typically contains various data, charts, and tables that can be used for validation testing. Individual datum and data found in tables typically includes airframe limitations (e.g., aerodynamic limitations, i.e., airspeeds, acceleration, altitude, and gross weight limits), V_x (best angle of climb), V_y (best rate of climb), stall speeds at differing configurations, and c.g. limitations. Data found in charts is typically performance oriented and includes takeoff, climb, range, endurance, descent, landing, mission planning (e.g., turn rate versus airspeed, turn radius versus airspeed), and emergency operation (e.g., glide). Simulator flight test data can then be collected in these areas and compared to the actual text datum/table data/chart data. Acceptable results could be considered to be within given POH

tolerances, chart resolution, Level D simulator equivalent values, or the ICAO default of 20% [9].

Classification Categories

It is proposed that flight model validation criteria be concisely described by a 4-tuple and simulation test personnel qualifications be described by a 3-tuple

$$\alpha | \beta | \gamma | \delta : \epsilon | \zeta | \eta$$

where the single-entry α field describes the intended use of the model, the β field lists the type of test primarily used in the validation, the γ field describes any affiliations the test team has with the aircraft model development personnel, and the δ

field summarizes the results of the test as detailed in Tables 1 through 4. (Note that table content is in no order of preference but rather is presented alphabetically where able.)

Table 1. Primary Use for Aircraft Model Field α

E	airspace efficiency
N	entertainment (e.g., video games)
P	pilot training
S	airspace safety analysis
T	other than pilot training (air traffic controller, maintenance, non-flying crew, etc.)
O	other

Table 2. Aircraft Model Validation (Primary) Test Type Field β

CERT	Certification, engineering, or experimental flight test techniques; i.e., primarily performance and handling qualities flight test
INSP	Visual observation of normal flight characteristics and performance (observation only; pilot not at the controls)
MAINT	Maintenance, production, acceptance, or functional test flight techniques
OPS	Operational flight maneuvers using Cooper-Harper handling qualities scale or similar
POH	Comparison to data, tables, and charts in the pilot’s operating handbook
SIM	Regulatory agency simulation certification procedures; e.g., FAA simulator, FTD, or PCATD qualification; i.e., primarily time-history data
Other	Validation technique not described by any of the above

Table 3. Aircraft Model Validation Test Objectivity Field γ

AFF	Test Lead and Simulation Engineering Test Pilot (unless not required due to INSP type test) affiliated in some way with the developer of the aircraft model or the aircraft manufacturer
OBJ	Objective third party Test Lead and Simulation Engineering Test Pilot (unless not required due to INSP-type test) not affiliated in any way with the developer of the aircraft model or the aircraft manufacturer

Table 4. Aircraft Model Validation Test Results Field δ

A	Aircraft simulation acceptable for use in designated application
C	Aircraft simulation conditionally acceptable for use in designated application; i.e., aircraft simulation acceptable with comments or exceptions for use in designated application
U	Aircraft simulation unacceptable for use in designated application

While many validation metrics can be gleaned from the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) [5] and the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) [7], when these are lacking these regulatory organizations prescribe the use of “engineering judgment.” Also, since these tolerances vary, when not specified, ICAO uses 20%. Finally, from the field of industrial engineering, specifically the area of gauge repeatability and reproducibility (R&R) analysis (and as guided by the Six Sigma Academy) acceptability criteria [10] are as follows:

- ≤ 10 percent error, system is acceptable
- > 10 percent and ≤ 30 percent error, system may be acceptable
- > 30 percent error, system needs improvement

Gage R&R is a statistical tool that measures the amount of variation in the measurement system arising from the measurement device and the people taking the measurement.

Continuing with the classification fields, the ϵ field lists the tester's level of pilot credentials, the ζ field lists the tester's level of flight test credentials, and the η field lists the tester's level of academic credentials. Additional details are given in Tables 5 through 7 below.

Table 5. Simulation Engineering Test Pilot (Unless INSP-Type Test, Then Test Lead Instead) Aviation Licensing Field ϵ

A	FAA Airman Certificate grade of Airline Transport Pilot
B	FAA Airman Certificate grade of Commercial Pilot and Instrument Pilot
C	FAA Airman Certificate grade of at least Private Pilot
D	Pilot experience, but less than holding an FAA Airman Certificate grade of Private Pilot
E	Aircrew experience
F	Other or none

Table 6. Simulation Engineering Test Pilot (Unless INSP-Type Test, Then Test Lead Instead) Flight Test Qualification Field ζ

A	Graduate of an Experimental Test Pilot long course or equivalent (as recognized by the Society of Experimental Test Pilots), or Graduate of a Maintenance Test Pilot (Maintenance Test Pilot/Production Test Pilot/Acceptance Test Pilot/Operational Check Flight Pilot/Functional Check Pilot) training program (e.g., military, Bell Helicopter- Textron, CST Berlin, etc.) and an Experimental Test Pilot short course (including academic training and hands-on experience in aircraft performance and handling qualities performed at a flight control station in an aircraft or simulator; e.g., National Test Pilot School, QinetiQ/Empire Test Pilots' School, Embry-Riddle University SIM 402, U.S. Naval Test Pilot School, University of Tennessee Space Institute, etc.)
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B	Graduate of an Experimental Test Pilot short course (including academic training and hands-on experience in aircraft performance and handling qualities performed at a flight control station in an aircraft or simulator; e.g., National Test Pilot School, QinetiQ/Empire Test Pilots' School, Embry-Riddle University SIM 402, U.S. Naval Test Pilot School, University of Tennessee Space Institute, etc.), or Graduate of a Maintenance Test Pilot (Maintenance Test Pilot/Production Test Pilot/Acceptance Test Pilot/Operational Check Flight Pilot/Functional Check Pilot) training program (e.g., military, Bell Helicopter- Textron, CST Berlin, etc.)
C	Graduate of an academic-only flight test course (aircraft performance, handling qualities, and data reduction, but with no hands-on experience; e.g., University of Kansas Continuing Education Aerospace Short Courses, Nova Defence, etc.)
D	Graduate of a flight test engineering course (flight test specific, but not necessarily aircraft performance, handling qualities, and data reduction; e.g., Royal Aeronautical Society, U.S. Air Force Test Pilot School, Society for Automotive Engineers International, etc.)
E	Graduate of a general test and evaluation course (e.g., International Test and Evaluation Association, Georgia Institute of Technology Test & Evaluation Research and Education Center, etc.)
F	Other or none

Table 7. Simulation Engineering Test Pilot (Unless INSP-Type Test, Then Test Lead Instead) Academic Field η

A	Earned engineering doctorate degree (Ph.D., D.Sc., or equivalent) from an ABET-accredited academic department
B	Earned engineering master's degree from an ABET-accredited academic department or designation as a registered Professional Engineer (P.E.)
C	Earned engineering graduate certificate from an ABET-accredited academic department
D	Earned engineering bachelor's degree from an ABET-accredited program
E	Earned bachelor's degree or higher
F	Other or none

To summarize, the 4-tuple provides information on the type of testing done while the triplet provides information on the person conducting/responsible for the testing. For example, testing of a general aircraft model in normal flight regimes and as part of an airspace queuing or efficiency simulation may result in recommended testing to S | INSP | AFF | C : F | D | E by the team Test Lead due to the software's intended usage and the generality of the aircraft model. A high-fidelity simulation model that is rapidly needed may justify testing to S | OPS | OBJ | C : B | E | D due to the amount of time required to complete CERT-level testing on all of the aircraft types, while a model used in training pilots in upper-level tasks may require testing to S | CERT | OBJ | A : A | C | D due to the software's intended usage, the critical nature of detailed aircraft performance within the simulation, the specificity of the aircraft model, and pending the availability of the experience and expertise of a level A | C | D pilot.

Summary

Due to the variety of aircraft simulation models available, their varied uses, and the lack of a clear validation standard, classification categories and a concise, seven-field format are proposed to succinctly inform the ultimate user of any aircraft simulation model as to the performance of the

model as well as the level of testing performed and the experience and qualifications of the tester or (or test team leader in the case of larger groups).

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